

Development of Interlocking Tiles from Recycled Plastic Waste Bottles

A.S. Kofarbai^a, J.E. Annune^{b*}, P.M. Laabe^c and M. B. Abdulazeez^d

^aScience Laboratory and Technology Research Department, Nigerian Building and Road Research Institute, North-West Zonal Office Kano, Kano State, Nigeria.

^bScience Laboratory and Technology Research Department, Nigerian Building and Road Research Institute, North-central Zonal Office Jos, Plateau State, Nigeria.

^cBuilding Research Department, Nigerian Building and Road Research Institute, North-central Zonal Office Jos, Plateau State, Nigeria.

^dRoad Research Department, Nigerian Building and Road Research Institute, North-central Zonal Office Jos, Plateau State, Nigeria.

Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration among all authors. All authors read and approved the final Manuscript.

Article Information

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20641249>

Open Peer Review History:

This journal follows the Advanced Open Peer Review policy. Identity of the Reviewers, Editor(s) and additional Reviewers, peer review

Comments, different versions of the manuscript, comments of the editors, etc are available here:

<https://pr.sdiarticle5.com/review-history/156z52>

Original Research Article

Received:

11/05/2026

Published:

01/06/2026

Abstract

Plastic waste constitutes a major environmental challenge, particularly in rapidly urbanizing regions such as Makurdi, Nigeria. In this study, recycled plastic waste bottles, predominantly high-density polyethylene (HDPE), were utilized as a binding material for the production of eco-friendly interlocking tiles, with river sand sourced from River Benue serving as the fine aggregate. Interlocking tile molds of suitable geometry were fabricated, and different mix proportions of plastic and sand were experimentally investigated.

*Corresponding author: E-mail: ericjighjigh@nbri.gov.ng

Cite as: Kofarbai, A. S., Annune, J. E., Laabe, P. M., & Abdulazeez, M. B. (2026). Development of interlocking tiles from recycled plastic waste bottles. *Journal of Scientific Research and Reports*, 32(5), 188–197. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20641249>

The production process involved sorting, cleaning, shredding, melting at a temperature of 300°C, and homogeneously mixing the constituents before casting and compaction in molds. The key engineering properties evaluated included flexural strength, compressive strength, density, and water absorption. The results showed that the optimum mix proportion of 70% plastic and 30% sand yielded the best performance, achieving a flexural strength of approximately 15.0–15.5 MPa and compressive strength in the range of 15–18 MPa. Additionally, the produced tiles exhibited zero water absorption due to the impermeable nature of the plastic matrix, and a relatively low density of about 1050–1100 kg/m³, classifying them as lightweight compared to conventional cement-based tiles. The findings indicate that recycled plastic interlocking tiles possess favorable mechanical and durability characteristics, making them suitable for applications such as walkways, pavements, and landscaping. The study concludes that recycled plastic waste can be effectively repurposed as a sustainable construction material, offering both environmental benefits and a viable alternative to traditional cement-based products.

Keywords: Recycled plastic, interlocking tiles, HDPE, sustainable construction, waste management.

1. Introduction

Municipal solid waste (MSW) comprises wastes generated from households, commercial establishments, institutions, municipal services, and industrial activities. The major constituents of MSW include organic matter, plastics, metals, glass, paper, textiles, and other discarded materials. Among these components, plastic waste has emerged as one of the most challenging environmental pollutants due to its extensive use, high production rate, and resistance to natural degradation. Globally, plastic production has exceeded 400 million tonnes annually, with a significant fraction ending up in landfills, drainage channels, rivers, and open dumpsites, thereby posing serious environmental and public health concerns [1; 2]. In Nigeria, rapid urbanization, population growth, and inadequate waste management infrastructure have contributed to the indiscriminate disposal of plastic waste in both urban and rural environments. Cities such as Makurdi generate substantial quantities of plastic waste daily, particularly from beverage containers, sachet water packaging, and household products. The accumulation of these materials in drainage systems and water bodies often results in flooding, environmental degradation, and ecosystem disruption. Consequently, there is an increasing need to develop sustainable and economically viable approaches for recycling plastic waste into value-added products.

Polyethylene-based plastics constitute a significant proportion of municipal plastic waste and are broadly categorized into Low-Density Polyethylene (LDPE) and High-Density Polyethylene (HDPE). LDPE is a thermoplastic polymer characterized by a highly branched molecular structure, low density between 0.91–0.94 g/cm³, excellent flexibility, and good chemical resistance. It is commonly used in plastic bags, sachet water packaging, films, and wrapping materials. However, its low mechanical strength and high volume of consumption contribute significantly to environmental pollution when improperly disposed of [3]. Conversely, HDPE possesses a more linear molecular structure with minimal branching, resulting in higher density between 0.94–0.97 g/cm³, greater tensile strength, superior stiffness, and enhanced chemical resistance compared to LDPE. HDPE is widely used in the manufacture of beverage bottles, detergent containers, pipes, and packaging products. Owing to its excellent durability, thermal stability, and mechanical performance, HDPE has attracted considerable attention as a potential binder material in composite construction products. The thermoplastic nature of HDPE allows it to soften and flow when heated, enabling it to encapsulate aggregate particles and form a dense matrix upon cooling. These characteristics make HDPE particularly suitable for the production of alternative construction materials such as paving blocks, bricks, and interlocking tiles [4].

Several researchers have investigated the utilization of recycled plastic waste in the construction industry as a means of reducing environmental pollution while conserving natural resources. [5]

reported that bricks produced from recycled polyethylene terephthalate (PET) and manufactured sand achieved compressive strengths suitable for building applications. Similarly, [6] produced paver blocks from waste plastics and demonstrated that plastic-based composites exhibited improved durability and reduced water absorption. [7] observed that recycled plastic tiles incorporating mineral aggregates achieved satisfactory mechanical properties and dimensional stability. Furthermore, [8] and [9] reported that incorporating recycled plastics into cementitious composites improved durability characteristics, reduced density, and enhanced resistance to moisture ingress.

The use of recycled plastic as a binding material offers several advantages over conventional cement-based systems. Plastic-based composites generally exhibit lower water absorption, enhanced resistance to chemical attack, improved durability under aggressive environmental conditions, and reduced carbon emissions associated with cement production. In addition, the conversion of plastic waste into construction materials will contribute to circular economy principles by diverting waste from landfills and reducing environmental pollution. Despite the growing body of research on plastic-based construction materials, limited studies have focused on the development of interlocking tiles using recycled plastic waste bottles and locally available river sand in Nigeria. Interlocking tiles are widely utilized for pedestrian walkways, pavements, parking areas, and landscaping applications because of their ease of installation, aesthetic appeal, and load-distribution characteristics. The development of sustainable interlocking tiles from locally sourced waste materials therefore presents an opportunity to address both environmental and infrastructural challenges.

This study investigates the development of eco-friendly interlocking tiles using recycled plastic waste bottles collected within Makurdi metropolis and river sand obtained from River Benue as the primary raw materials. The research evaluates the suitability of recycled HDPE plastic as a binding material, determines the optimum plastic-sand mix ratio, and assesses the physical, mechanical, and microstructural properties of the produced interlocking tiles.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials and Equipment

The materials utilized in this study were locally sourced within Makurdi metropolis, Nigeria, ensuring cost-effectiveness and environmental relevance. The primary raw materials included recycled plastic waste (HDPE), river sand obtained from River Benue, and, where applicable, minor quantities of gravel. The plastic waste comprised predominantly discarded plastic bottles collected from streets, drainage systems, dumpsites, residential areas, and commercial locations. These plastics were selected due to their abundance and environmental impact. The sand used as fine aggregate was sharp river sand with particle sizes ranging between 0.15 mm and 4.75 mm, ensuring adequate gradation for improved bonding and packing density. The equipment employed for the experimental process included Metal molds (interlocking geometry), Melting barrels/furnace, a digital Weighing scale, Hand trowel, Metal stirrer, Personal protective equipment (PPE), an electric oven from the Nigerian Building and Road Research Institute, North-Central Zonal Office, Jos.

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Collection and Sorting

Plastic waste materials were collected as previously studied by [13] from multiple municipal solid waste dumpsites within Makurdi. The collected plastics were manually sorted to separate high-density polyethylene (HDPE) from other polymer types such as LDPE and PET. Contaminants such as bottle caps, labels, and organic debris were removed.

2.2.2 Cleaning, Drying and Shredding

The sorted plastic materials were washed thoroughly using water and detergent to eliminate dirt, grease, and other impurities that could adversely affect bonding. The cleaned plastics were then air-dried to remove moisture. The dried plastic waste was shredded into smaller pieces (approximately 1–2 cm in size) to facilitate uniform melting and mixing as also reported by [14].

2.3 Melting and Mixing Process

The cleaned and shredded plastic waste bottles (HDPE) were introduced into a metallic melting chamber and heated at a controlled temperature of approximately 300°C until a uniform molten state was achieved. The selected temperature was sufficient to ensure complete melting and adequate flowability of the plastic matrix while preventing thermal degradation of the polymer [4; 10]. Throughout the melting process, continuous mechanical stirring was maintained to promote uniform heat distribution, enhance homogeneity, and minimize localized overheating.

Upon achieving a fully molten plastic phase, pre-weighed quantities of River Benue sand were gradually introduced into the melt in accordance with the predetermined mix proportions. The composite mixture was continuously stirred to ensure uniform dispersion of sand particles within the molten plastic matrix. This process facilitated effective wetting and encapsulation of the aggregate particles by the thermoplastic binder, thereby improving interfacial bonding and reducing the occurrence of voids within the composite structure [8; 11].

The molten composite was further mixed until a homogeneous consistency was obtained, indicating uniform distribution of the constituent materials. Adequate mixing is essential in plastic-sand composites as it promotes particle interlocking, enhances load transfer between the plastic matrix and aggregate phase, and contributes to improved mechanical performance and durability of the finished interlocking tiles [6; 9]. The resulting homogeneous mixture was subsequently transferred into prepared molds for casting and compaction.

2.4 Mix Proportions and Experimental Design

Different mix ratios of plastic to sand were investigated to determine the optimum composition. The primary ratios of plastic to sand evaluated were 50:50, 25:75 and 75:25. In addition, composite blends incorporating multiple plastic types were explored to improve mechanical performance. Preliminary trials indicated that a blend ratio of plastic to sand within the range of 50:50 to 70:30 provided the most favorable results in terms of strength and durability.

2.5 Casting and Molding

The molds were cleaned, dried, and lubricated using waste engine oil to prevent adhesion of the composite material. The molten plastic – aggregate mixture was then carefully poured into preheated molds. Compaction was carried out manually using a metal compactor to eliminate entrapped air and ensure uniform density. The mixture was evenly distributed within the mold to achieve the desired interlocking tile geometry.

2.6 Setting and Cooling Process

After casting, the tiles were allowed to cool and solidify under ambient conditions. The setting process involved gradual cooling, during which the molds were gently agitated to prevent sticking and ensure

proper edge formation with an average cooling time of 60 minutes. After complete solidification, the tiles were demolded and allowed to cool further to attain structural stability.

2.7.1 Testing Procedures

The produced interlocking tiles were subjected to the following laboratory tests to evaluate their engineering properties such as Compressive Strength Test, Flexural Strength Test, Water Absorption Test and Density Measurement in accordance with [13], [14] and [19].

2.8 Data Analysis

The experimental results were analyzed by comparing the performance of different mix ratios. Parameters such as strength, water absorption, and durability were used as criteria for determining the optimum composition. The best-performing mix was identified based on its ability to combine high mechanical strength, low water absorption, and structural stability.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Mechanical and Physical Properties

The engineering properties of the produced interlocking tiles are presented in Table 1. The results indicate that the plastic-to-sand ratio significantly influenced the mechanical strength, density, and water absorption characteristics of the composite tiles. As the plastic content increased from 30% to 70%, both compressive and flexural strengths improved considerably, while density and water absorption decreased.

Table 1: Engineering Properties of the Samples

Mix Ratio	Compressive Strength (MPa)	Flexural Strength (MPa)	Density (kg/m ³)	Water Absorption (%)
30P:70S	9.5	8.2	1480	1.8
50P:50S	13.2	11.7	1260	0.4
70P:30S	17.1	15.3	1080	0.0

The 30P:70S mixture exhibited the lowest compressive strength of 9.5 MPa and flexural strength of 8.2 MPa as shown in Figure 1 and 2 respectively, which can be attributed to the insufficient amount of molten plastic available to fully coat and bind the sand particles. This resulted in poor interfacial bonding and the presence of microvoids within the composite matrix. Similar observations were reported by [6], who found that inadequate plastic content reduced the cohesion between aggregate particles, leading to lower strength values in plastic-based paving blocks.

An increase in plastic content to 50% resulted in improved compressive strength of 13.2 MPa and flexural strength of 11.7 MPa, indicating better particle encapsulation and enhanced load transfer within the composite structure. However, the optimum performance was achieved at the 70P:30S mix ratio, which recorded the highest compressive strength of 17.1 MPa and flexural strength of 15.3 MPa. The superior performance of this mixture can be attributed to the formation of a continuous plastic matrix that effectively encapsulated the sand particles, reduced internal voids, and improved stress distribution under loading. Similar findings were reported by [5] and [7], who observed that higher plastic contents improved the mechanical properties of plastic-based construction composites by enhancing particle bonding and reducing porosity.

The compressive strength obtained for the optimum mix 17.1 MPa as presented in Figure 1 satisfies the minimum requirements for light-duty and medium-duty pavement applications. According to the requirements of the Nigerian Industrial Standard (NIS 87:2007) [15], and the British Standard BS EN 1338:2003 [16] for concrete paving blocks, paving units intended for pedestrian walkways, residential pavements, and landscaping applications should possess adequate strength and durability to

withstand service loads. Although the present composite tiles are non-cementitious materials, their compressive strength falls within the range reported for commercial plastic pavers and is suitable for pedestrian and low-traffic applications. Furthermore, the flexural strength of 15.3 MPa shown in Figure 2 exceeds values reported for many conventional concrete paving products, indicating excellent resistance to bending and crack propagation.

Figure 1: Compressive Strength of the Mix Ratios

Figure 2: Flexural Strength of the Mix Ratios

Figure 3: Density Variation of the Mix Ratios

Figure 4: Water Content of the Different Mix Ratios

The density of the tiles decreased from 1480 kg/m³ to 1080 kg/m³ with increasing plastic content as shown in Figure 3. This reduction is attributed to the lower specific gravity of HDPE compared to natural sand. The densities obtained are considerably lower than those of conventional concrete paving blocks (typically 2200–2400 kg/m³), indicating that the produced tiles can be classified as lightweight composite construction materials. Similar density reductions have been reported by [17] and [9] when recycled plastics were incorporated into construction composites.

The result of water absorption decreased significantly as the plastic content increased, with the optimum mix exhibiting zero water absorption as shown in Figure 4. This behavior is attributed to the hydrophobic nature of HDPE, which forms an impermeable matrix around the sand particles and prevents moisture ingress. According to ASTM C140 [20] and BS EN 1338 [16] recommendations, lower water absorption is associated with improved durability, freeze-thaw resistance, and long-term performance. The zero water absorption obtained in this study is superior to the typical 5–8% water absorption reported for conventional concrete paving blocks and agrees with the findings of [8] and

[11], who reported negligible water absorption in plastic-based composites due to the impermeable nature of thermoplastic binders.

Overall, the results demonstrate that the 70P:30S mix ratio provides the most favorable combination of strength, durability, and lightweight characteristics, making it the optimum composition for the production of recycled plastic interlocking tiles suitable for walkways, pedestrian pavements, landscaping works, and other light-to-medium duty construction applications.

Figure 5: FTIR Spectrum of HDPE Sample

The FTIR spectrum of the recycled HDPE used as the binding matrix for the interlocking tiles is presented in Figure 5. The results confirmed the preservation of the polymer's chemical structure after recycling and thermal processing. The prominent absorption bands at 2913 cm^{-1} and 2847 cm^{-1} correspond to the asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of aliphatic $-\text{CH}_2-$ groups, which are characteristic of polyethylene materials. The peak at 1465 cm^{-1} is attributed to CH_2 bending vibrations, while the strong absorption band at 721 cm^{-1} represents the rocking vibration of long methylene chains, indicating the semi-crystalline nature of HDPE. A weak band observed around 1742 cm^{-1} suggests the presence of minor carbonyl groups formed through limited thermo-oxidative degradation during melting, whereas the broad peak at 3743 cm^{-1} may be associated with traces of hydroxyl groups from absorbed moisture or slight surface oxidation. The absence of significant new functional groups demonstrates that the recycling process did not substantially alter the molecular structure of the polymer, which agrees with the findings of [3], [21], and [8]. This structural stability contributes to the excellent durability, chemical resistance, and negligible water absorption exhibited by the produced plastic-sand interlocking tiles, thereby validating the suitability of recycled HDPE as an effective binder for sustainable construction applications.

Figure 6: SEM Micrograph of the Three Mix Ratios (a) 30P:70S, (b) 50P:50S, (c) 70P:30S

The SEM micrographs presented in Figure 6 (a-c) of the recycled plastic–sand interlocking tiles revealed significant differences in microstructural characteristics as the plastic-to-sand ratio varied. The microstructure of the 30P:70S sample exhibited a relatively rough and heterogeneous surface with noticeable microvoids and poorly encapsulated sand particles, indicating insufficient plastic binder to fully coat and bond the aggregate particles. This resulted in weak interfacial adhesion and increased pore spaces, which explain the lower compressive strength (9.5 MPa), flexural strength (8.2 MPa), and higher water absorption (1.8%) observed for this mix. In contrast, the 50P:50S composition showed improved particle distribution and reduced void content due to the increased availability of molten plastic, leading to better interfacial bonding between the sand particles and the polymer matrix. The SEM image revealed a more compact structure with fewer discontinuities, which corresponded to the improved mechanical properties recorded experimentally. The 70P:30S sample exhibited the most homogeneous and dense microstructure, characterized by excellent encapsulation of sand particles within the continuous plastic matrix, minimal microcracks, and negligible voids. The enhanced interfacial adhesion and compact morphology facilitated efficient stress transfer throughout the composite, resulting in the highest compressive strength (17.1 MPa) and flexural strength (15.3 MPa) as well as zero water absorption. Similar observations have been reported by [8], [17], and [11], who found that increasing polymer content improves matrix continuity, reduces porosity, and enhances the mechanical performance of plastic-based construction composites. Therefore, the SEM analysis confirms that the superior engineering performance of the 70P:30S interlocking tile is directly associated with its dense, well-bonded, and low-porosity microstructure.

4. Conclusion

In conclusion, this study successfully demonstrated the feasibility of producing sustainable interlocking tiles from recycled HDPE plastic bottles and river sand, providing an effective alternative to conventional cement-based paving units. The experimental results showed that the plastic-to-sand ratio significantly influenced the engineering performance of the tiles, with increasing plastic content enhancing compressive strength, flexural strength, and structural integrity while simultaneously reducing density and water absorption. The optimum performance was achieved at the 70P:30S mix ratio, which exhibited the highest compressive strength of 17.1 MPa, flexural strength of 15.3 MPa, negligible water absorption, and a dense, well-bonded microstructure as confirmed by SEM analysis. These properties indicate excellent durability, lightweight characteristics, and resistance to moisture ingress, making the developed tiles suitable for pedestrian walkways, landscaping, and light-to-medium duty pavement applications. Furthermore, the study highlights the environmental benefits of diverting plastic waste from landfills and transforming it into value-added construction materials, thereby contributing to sustainable waste management and circular economy practices.

Disclaimer (Artificial Intelligence)

Author(s) hereby declare that NO generative AI technologies such as Large Language Models (ChatGPT, COPILOT, etc.) and text-to-image generators have been used during the writing or editing of this manuscript.

Competing Interests

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

References

- [1] Azoulay, D., Villa, P., Arellano, Y., Gordon, M. F., Moon, D., Miller, K. A., & Kistler, A. (2019). *Plastic and health: The hidden costs of a plastic planet*. Center for International Environmental Law. <https://www.ciel.org/plasticandhealth>
- [2] Evode, N., Qamar, S. A., Bilal, M., Barceló, D., & Iqbal, H. M. N. (2021). Plastic waste and its management strategies for environmental sustainability. *Case Studies in Chemical and Environmental Engineering*, 4, 100142. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cscee.2021.100142>
- [3] Roslan, S. A. H. (2013). *The effect of recycled high-density polyethylene (HDPE) mixing ratio on the tensile strength of high-density polyethylene (HDPE) polymer* (Doctoral dissertation, Universiti Malaysia Pahang). <http://umpir.ump.edu.my/id/eprint/7627/1/CD7757.pdf>
- [4] Thakare, K. A., Vishwakarma, H. G., & Bhave, A. G. (2015). Experimental investigation of possible use of HDPE as thermal storage material in thermal storage type solar cookers. *International Journal of Research in Engineering and Technology*, 4, 92–99. <https://doi.org/10.15623/ijret.2015.0412019>
- [5] Aiswaria, K., Abdulla, K., Akhil, E. B., Lashmi, H. G., & Timmy, J. (2018). Manufacturing and experimental investigation of bricks with plastic and M-sand. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology*, 7(6), 6558–6562. <https://doi.org/10.15680/IJRSET.2018.0706026>
- [6] Ghude, A., Kant, R., Jaiswal, P., Dhohne, A., Thool, A., Nandanwar, S., & Bele, K. (2019). Utilization of waste plastic in paver blocks. *International Journal of Advanced Research and Innovative Ideas in Education*, 5, 2395–2396. <https://www.irjet.net/archives/V7/i7/IRJET-V7I7393.pdf>
- [7] Balamurugan, G., & Rafi, I. M. (2021). An experimental study on plastic paver tiles. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology*. <https://doi.org/10.15680/IJRSET>
- [8] Benimam, S., Bentchikou, M., Debieb, F., Kenai, S., & Guendouz, M. (2021). Physical and mechanical properties of cement mortar with LLDPE powder and PET fiber wastes. *Advances in Concrete Construction*, 12(6), 461–467. <https://doi.org/10.12989/acc.2021.12.6.461>
- [9] Blaifi, H., Guendouz, M., Belhadj, A. E., Boukhelkhal, D., & Hadjadj, M. (2023). Sustainable use of recycled plastic and ceramic industrial wastes in eco-friendly construction material. *Environmental Engineering and Management Journal*, 22(8). <https://doi.org/10.30638/eemj.2023.124>
- [10] Brydson, J. A. (1995). *Plastics materials* (7th ed.). Butterworth-Heinemann.
- [11] Puttaraj, M. H., Parangi, B., Gagan, M. S., Shivu, S., & Hallur, M. S. (2020). Reuse of plastic waste for the production of floor tiles. *Journal of Seybold Report*, 15(8). <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/344338355>
- [12] American Society for Testing and Materials. (2016b). *ASTM D790: Standard test methods for flexural properties of unreinforced and reinforced plastics and electrical insulating materials*. ASTM International. <https://doi.org/10.1520/D0790-10>
- [13] American Society for Testing and Materials. (2016a). *ASTM C1492-03: Standard specification for concrete roof tile*. ASTM International. <https://doi.org/10.1520/C1492-03R16>

- [14] Abdel Tawab, O. F., Amin, M. R., Ibrahim, M. M., Abdel Wahab, M., & Abd El Rahman, E. N. (2020). Recycling waste plastic bags as a replacement for cement in building materials. *Journal of Waste Resources and Recycling*, 1(2), 1–13.
- [15] Standards Organisation of Nigeria. (2007). *Nigerian Industrial Standard NIS 87:2007: Specification for concrete paving blocks*. Standards Organisation of Nigeria (SON).
- [16] British Standards Institution. (2003). *BS EN 1338:2003: Concrete paving blocks—Requirements and test methods*. British Standards Institution.
- [17] Guendouz, M., Debieb, F., Boukendakdji, O., Kadri, E. H., Bentchikou, M., & Soualhi, H. (2016). Use of plastic waste in sand concrete. *Journal of Materials and Environmental Science*, 7(2), 382–389. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/298076109>
- [18] EN 14617-1. (2005). *Determination of apparent density and water absorption*. Slovenski Standards.
- [19] Nwosu, C. N., Nwankwo, V. O., Okechukwu, C., & Nwankwo, N. E. (2022). Development of composite floor tiles through the blending of waste sachets, PET bottles and sand aggregates. *IRE Journals*, 5(7), 412–418. <https://www.irejournals.com>
- [20] ASTM International. (2016). *ASTM C140/C140M-16: Standard test methods for sampling and testing concrete masonry units and related units*. ASTM International. https://doi.org/10.1520/C0140_C0140M-16
- [21] Ingabire, D., Ntthemuka, F., Mugabo, G., Isabane, R. S., & Turatimana, T. (2018). Recycling High-Density Polyethylene (HDPE) into construction materials as a key step in plastic waste reduction: case of Kigali City. *Rwanda Journal of Engineering, Science, Technology and Environment*, 1(1). <https://doi.org/10.4314/rjeste.v1i1.2s>
- [22] Qassid, A. F., & Al-Khashab, H. A. (2025). Producing eco-friendly tiles from recycled plastic generated from municipal solid waste. *Journal of Environmental Research, Engineering and Management*, 81(1), 58–65. <https://doi.org/10.5755/j01.arem.81.1.35353>

Disclaimer/Publisher’s Note: The statements, opinions and data contained in all publications are solely those of the individual author(s) and contributor(s) and not of the publisher and/or the editor(s). This publisher and/or the editor(s) disclaim responsibility for any injury to people or property resulting from any ideas, methods, instructions or products referred to in the content.

© Copyright (2026): Author(s). The licensee is the journal publisher. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Peer-review history:

The peer review history for this paper can be accessed here:

<https://pr.sdiarticle5.com/review-history/156852>